

500+ definitions

EVIDENCE BASED CO-CREATION
FOR PUBLIC HEALTH

474 definitions of Co-production/ Co-design

Masterson et al. (2022), DOI: 10.1111/hex.13470

30 definitions of Co-creation

Messiha, K (2021). Health CASCADE. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6818098

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement n° 956501